

Sign Language Translation Using Deep Learning

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Abstract - The advancement of technology has brought significant improvements in communication tools for people with disabilities, particularly the deaf and hard-of-hearing community. The integration of deep learning techniques, particularly in computer vision and natural language processing, has emerged as a promising solution to automate and enhance the process of sign language translation. This paper explores the application of deep learning algorithms in the development of an efficient and accurate sign language translation system, focusing on leveraging Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks for dynamic gesture recognition and translation. The advancement of technology has brought significant improvements in communication tools for people with disabilities, particularly the deaf and hard-of-hearing community. The integration of deep learning techniques, particularly in computer vision and natural language processing, has emerged as a promising solution to automate and enhance the process of sign language translation. This project explores the application of deep learning algorithms in the development of an efficient and accurate sign language translation system, focusing on leveraging convolutional neural networks for dynamic gesture recognition and translation

Key_word: sign language translation, convolutional neural networks , long short-term memory, natural language processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Sign language translation is a vital area of research aiming to bridge communication gaps between the Deaf and hard-of-hearing communities and those who use spoken languages. Traditional sign languages rely on a complex blend of hand gestures, facial expressions, and body movements to convey meaning, making automated translation a challenging task. However, recent advances in deep learning have created new opportunities to address these challenges by leveraging computer vision, natural language processing, and machine learning techniques. Deep learning models, particularly those using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for spatial feature extraction and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) or transformer-based architectures for temporal sequence modeling, have shown promise in recognizing and translating sign language gestures from video inputs. These models can analyze sequences of hand and body movements, identify key patterns, and generate corresponding translations in spoken or written language. Despite the progress, sign language translation remains a complex problem due to the vast number of unique signs, the nuances of regional sign variations, and the intricacies of facial expressions and body posture. Therefore, recent research

also explores multimodal approaches, combining hand pose estimation, facial recognition, and attention mechanisms to improve accuracy and fluency in translation. Through continued advancements, deep learning has significant potential to make sign language translation more accessible and accurate, fostering inclusive communication and accessibility for Deaf and hearing communities alike. neural networks to produce plausible results in translation and video generation tasks. In fact, the proposed ideology further extends to developing user interface-based applications for handling real-time cases and potentially addressing the various challenges of existing approaches. Our contributions comprise the creation of Indian Sign Language (ISL) related sentence level video datasets using multiple signers without involving any specialized components like color gloves and sensors. We used a digital SLR camera and web camera devices. These models can learn to identify key features for video data, process temporal sequence and translate message places safer by offering better control over gas appliances. Sign language is a complex visual language that involves hand gestures, facial expressions, and body movements to convey meaning. While it's a vital tool for communication for millions of deaf and hard-of-hearing individuals worldwide, it often creates barriers in mainstream society. Deep learning, a subset of artificial intelligence, has revolutionized various fields, including natural language processing and computer vision. By leveraging its power,

II. RELATED WORKS

[1] Convolutional neural networks were used and segmented hand images/videos were used as an input to them. 36 static hand gestures from Indian Sign Language were trained and a classification accuracy of 98.81% was achieved on the test data. This model also showed a good performance when we transfer learned the American Sign Language giving a classification accuracy of 97.71%. LSTM with a convolutional kernel was used for training 10 dynamic gestures. This model achieved a classification accuracy of 99.08%. But as soon as we implemented this system, we figured out there is an inherent problem with this methodology.

[2]. Towards this end, we introduce How2Sign, a multimodal and multiview continuous American Sign Language (ASL) dataset, consisting of a parallel corpus of more than 80 hours of sign language videos and a set of corresponding modalities including speech, English transcripts, and depth. A three-hour subset was further recorded in the Panoptic studio enabling detailed 3D pose estimation. To evaluate the potential of How2Sign for real-world impact, we conduct a study with ASL signers and show that synthesized videos using our dataset can indeed be understood. The study further gives insights on challenges that computer vision should address in order to make progress in this field.

[3]. Vision-based sign language recognition aims at helping deaf people to communicate with others. However, most existing sign language datasets are limited to a small number of words. Due to the

limited vocabulary size, models learned from those datasets cannot be applied in practice. In this paper, we introduce a new large-scale Word-Level American Sign Language (WLASL) video dataset, containing more than 2000 words performed by over 100 signers. Our results show that pose-based and appearance-based models achieve comparable performances up to 66% at top-10 accuracy on 2,000 words/glosses, demonstrating the validity and challenges of our dataset.

[11]. Most of the existing continuous SLR methods are extensions of the isolated word SLR methods. These methods use the isolated word SLR results as the basic module and obtain the sentence recognition results through sentence segmentation and word alignment. However, sentence segmentation and word alignment are often not accurate, resulting in a low sentence recognition accuracy. At the same time, continuous SLR usually requires strict sample labels, leading to the difficult task of manual labeling and limited training data availability

[13]. The instrumented glove has five flex sensors, an inertial sensor, and two contact sensors (made with silver-coated fabric). For data acquisition, five volunteers performed gestures in Libras. In the proposed segmentation technique, the collected data were segmented into three periods (fixed amounts of signal samples): construction period, alphabet gesture, and relaxation period. The periods of alphabet gesture are submitted to segmentation, and the classifier was designed to recognize the 26 letters of alphabet. Different classifiers were employed to classify the gestures and analyze the system in different scenarios. For the classification in group of sensors, the highest performance obtained was an accuracy of 96.15% with Random Forest (RF) classifier.

[14]. This paper makes the following contributions. First, we propose a new framework for single modality networks in dynamic hand gesture recognition task to learn from multiple modalities. This framework results in a Multimodal Training / Unimodal Testing (MTUT) scheme. Second, we introduce the SSA loss to share the knowledge of single modality networks. Third, we develop the focal regularization parameter for avoiding negative transfer. In our experiments, we show that learning with our method improves the test time performance of unimodal networks

III. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

1) PROPOSED BLOCK DIAGRAM

The proposed system for sign language translation leverages advanced deep learning techniques to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of translating sign language into text or speech. It employs a hybrid architecture that integrates convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for spatial feature extraction from video frames and long short-term memory (LSTM) networks or transformers for capturing temporal dynamics in sign language. The system utilizes a comprehensive dataset that includes diverse sign language variations, gestures, and associated contextual information to train the model effectively. Additionally, it incorporates real-time processing capabilities, enabling instantaneous translation of sign language in live interactions. By integrating user feedback and continuous learning mechanisms, the system aims to improve its adaptability and performance over time, addressing the challenges posed by different signing

styles and regional dialects. The project commences phase of requirement specification that outlines the critical components, goals, user requirements, and any constraints. The hardware consists of the CAM module, a cost-effective camera that features a Wi-Fi-enabled microcontroller, which is vital for capturing images and video streaming. To facilitate programming and debugging, a USB-to-serial converter is utilized to enable communication between the CAM and a computer. SSD Or HDD both are quick store.

Figure 1. Proposed block diagram

Image Capture: The process begins with image capture, where the ESP32 CAM module actively records images or streams video. This camera is a strategically positioned to monitor capturing clear visuals of all hand gesture data. The main design methodology for this project is described below. The methodology for developing a sign language translation system involves several key steps. First, a diverse dataset of sign language videos is collected and annotated with corresponding text or spoken language translations. This data is then preprocessed to normalize inputs and segment gestures for model training.

Feature Detection: After obtaining images, the next step is feature detection. In this phase, the system analyzes the captured visuals to identify key features that characterize the objects within the images. This involves recognizing various attributes such as edges, shapes, colors, and hand gesture, which help in distinguishing one symbol from another. Effective feature detection is critical, as it allows the system to interpret the image content accurately, paving the way for more advanced processing techniques to follow.

2)DESIGN FLOW

Next ,deep learning models are developed, utilizing conventional Neural Networks(CNN) to extract spatial features from video frames and Recurrent Neural Networks(RNN) or Transformer to

handle the temporal sequence of gestures and ensure contextual accuracy. The models are trained annotated datasets, with optimization techniques applied to enhance performance and generalization. CNN-LSTM hybrid model can extract features from each frame and an LSTM relationship across frames. The hybrid model works Continuous sign language or continuous defines phrases or sentences as labels while static individual gestures use single-word labels to split data into training, validation, and testing sets ensuring the model generalizes to unseen signs. The recognized gestures are then translated into spoken language using natural language processing (NLP) and text-to-speech synthesis. The system integrates a user-friendly interface for sign language input via camera or sensor and translated output via text or speech. Testing and evaluation involve assessing accuracy, response time, and user feedback. The system is deployed on selected

Figure 2. Flow diagram

platforms/devices, with regular updates and maintenance ensuring optimal performance. Finally, the trained models are integrated into a user-friendly application that provides real-time translation of sign language into text or spoken language, enabling effective communication and interaction.

IV.RESULT ANALYSIS

The results of a sign language translation system using deep learning have shown promising advancements in recognizing and translating sign language gestures into text or speech. Deep learning models, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for feature extraction and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks for temporal modeling, have demonstrated high accuracy in recognizing individual signs and sequences. The use of pose estimation and hand tracking further enhances the system’s ability to distinguish between various gestures and handshapes. While these models perform well on structured datasets, real-world scenarios present challenges, including variations in signing styles, differences in lighting conditions, and the need for understanding contextual cues. Despite these obstacles, ongoing improvements in model architectures and training techniques are contributing to more robust and real-time sign language translation systems that can

significantly aid communication for the Deaf and hard-of-hearing communities.

Figure 3. Hand tracking and recognition

V. CONCLUSION

Research in machine learning and computer vision has advanced sign language recognition through methods like neural networks, CNN, and LSTM. A proposed system focuses on hand tracking, detecting hands based on skin color and lighting conditions, using ANN to classify alphabet images with 94% accuracy. It also incorporates speech to convert recognized sign text into speech for blind individuals. This application enables deaf individuals to communicate with the hearing anywhere. The system bridges communication gaps between different abilities, allowing interactions between silent, hearing-impaired, blind, and normal individuals. This Gesture technology represents an exciting frontier in human-computer interaction and has the potential to change the way we interact with technology and each other. With continuous innovation and improvement, it can become a valuable tool for improving accessibility, efficiency, and user experience in many applications. Although the concept is promising, there are still challenges to overcome, such as ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the gestures. recognize, adapt to different cultural gestures and nuances, and resolve privacy issues related to the use of gesture data. Moreover, further research and development is needed to refine the technology, optimize its effectiveness in

different contexts, and seamlessly integrate it into existing systems.

REFERENCES

1. P. Likhari, N. K. Bhagat, and G. N. Rathna, "Deep learning methods for Indian sign language recognition," in Proc. IEEE 10th Int. Conf. Consum. Electron. (ICCE-Berlin), Nov. 2020, pp. 1–6.
2. Giro-i-Nieto, "How2Sign: A large-scale multimodal dataset for continuous American sign language," in Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit., Jun. 2021,
3. D. Li, C. Rodriguez, X. Yu, and H. Li, "Word-level deep sign language recognition from video: A new large-scale dataset and methods comparison," in Proc. IEEE/CVF winter Conf. Appl. Computer. Vis., Mar. 2020, pp. 1459–1469.
4. R. H. Randhawa, N. Aslam, M. Alauth man, IV, April 2018- Available at www.ijraset.com 2990 IJRASET (UGC Approved Journal): All Rights are Reserved A Review on Gesture Vocalizer Deena Nath1, Jitendra Kurmi2, Deveki Nandan Shukla3 1, 2, 3Department of Computer Science, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University Lucknow.
5. H. Rafiq, and F. Comeau, "Security hardening of botnet detectors using generative adversarial networks," IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 78276–78292, 2021.
6. J. Ryu, and J.-H. Kim, "Short-range radar based real-time hand gesture recognition using LSTM encoder," IEEE Access, vol. 7, pp. 33610–33618, 2019.
7. A. Gayathri, Dr. A. Sasi Kumar2 1PG Scholar," Sign Language Recognition for Deaf and Dumb People Using Android Environment", International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET)ISSN: 2321 - 9653; IC Value: 45.98; SJ Impact Factor: 6.887 Volume 6 Issue.
8. Suthagar.S.,K.S.Tamilselvan, P. Balakumar, B.Jalakshmi, C.Roshin," Translation of Sign Language for Deaf and Dumb People", International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE) ISSN: 2277- 3878, Volume-8Issue-5, January 2020

9. Sakshi Goyal, Ishita Sharma, Shanu Sharma, "Sign Language Recognition System For Deaf And Dumb People", International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT) ISSN: 2278-0181 Vol. 2 Issue 4, ASET,
10. T.-H. Chan, K. Jia, S. Gao, J. Lu, Z. Zeng, and Y. Ma, "PCANet: A simple deep learning baseline for image classification?" IEEE Trans. Image Process., vol. 24, no. 12, pp. 5017–5032, Dec. 2015.
11. Q. Xiao, X. Chang, X. Zhang, and X. Liu, "Multi-information spatial-temporal LSTM fusion continuous sign language neural machine translation," IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 216718–216728, 2020
12. N. C. Camgoz, S. Hadfield, O. Koller, H. Ney, and R. Bowden, "Neuralsign language translation," in Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit., Jun. 2018, pp. 7784–7793.
13. T. S. Dias, J. J. A. M. Júnior, and S. F. Pichorim, "An instrumented glove for recognition of Brazilian sign language alphabet," IEEE Sensors J., vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 2518–2529, 2021.
14. M. Abavisani, H. R. V. Joze, and V. M. Patel, "Improving the performance of unimodal dynamic hand-gesture recognition with multimodal training," in Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR), Jun. 2019, pp. 1165–1174.
15. Chen, Y. Li, R. Hu, X. Zhang, and X. Chen, "Hand gesture recognition based on surface electromyography using convolutional neural network with transfer learning method," IEEE J. Biomed. Health Informat., vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 1292–1304, Apr. 2021.